

Silica gel-mediated microwave-assisted efficient synthesis of highly substituted imidazoles and exploration of naked eye/colorimetric sensor for anions

Pranabes Bhattacharyya, Arunima Medda, Anuva Samanta, Nikhil Guchhait and Asish R. Das*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : archem@caluniv.ac.in, ardas66@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 09 November 2010, revised 29 December 2010, accepted 30 December 2010

Abstract : Ammonium formate and silica gel have been found to be efficient reagent combination for an improved and very rapid one-pot synthesis of 2,4,5-trisubstituted and 1,2,4,5-tetrasubstituted imidazoles in excellent yields. Multicomponent condensation in the presence of solid support with operational simplicity, inexpensive reagents, high yield of products, tolerance of sensitive functionalities, use of non-hazardous and non-toxic reagents combination under solventless condition makes this synthetic protocol, an attractive one. Moreover, trisubstituted imidazole, 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1*H*-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazo-phenol or tetrasubstituted imidazole, 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1-thiazol-2-yl)-1*H*-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazo-phenol have been found to be naked eye and colorimetric sensor for anions like F⁻, Cl⁻, CH₃COO⁻, H₂PO₄⁻ offering very high binding constant with F⁻ ion ($K = 1.39 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$).

Keywords : Imidazoles, ammonium formate (ammonia donor), silica gel, cyclocondensation, supported reagent, anion sensor.

Introduction

The imidazole structural unit is one of the most important nucleus found in a large number of natural products and pharmacologically active molecules¹⁻⁵ and the members of this family are known to possess NO synthase inhibition and antifungal, antimycotic, antibiotic, antiulcerative, antitumor, antibacterial and CB1 receptor antagonistic activities^{6,7}. Various substituted imidazoles act as inhibitors of p38 MAP kinase⁸ and B-Raf kinase⁹, glucagon receptors¹⁰, plant growth regulators¹¹, therapeutic agents¹², and pesticides¹³. Following that, a number of synthetic methods appeared in the literature for the construction of this important structural core. Recently, multicomponent reactions (MCRs) have attracted much attention since they are performed without isolation of the intermediate and in turn save both energy and raw materials coupled with reduction in time¹⁴. Radziszewski and Japp reported the first synthesis of highly substituted imidazoles from a 1,2-dicarbonyl compound, different aldehydes, and ammonia^{15,16}. Quite a good number of methods have been developed also for the synthesis of 1,2,4,5-tetrasubstituted imidazoles and 2,4,5-trisubstituted imidazoles. The 1,2,4,5-tetrasubstituted imidazoles are

carried out by four-component condensation involving 1,2-diketone/ α -hydroxyketone, an aldehyde, primary amine and ammonium acetate using microwaves¹⁷, molecular iodine¹⁸, HClO₄-SiO₂¹⁹, heteropolyacid^{20,21}, silica gel/NaHSO₄²², L-proline²³, FeCl₃.6H₂O²⁴, BF₃.SiO₂²⁵, mercaptopropyl silica²⁶ and silica-supported Wells-Dawson acid²⁷. In addition; they can also be accessed by the condensation of a 1,2-diketone with an aryl nitride and primary amine under microwave irradiation²⁸, by hetero-Cope rearrangement²⁹, and by *N*-alkylation of trisubstituted imidazoles³⁰. Three-component cyclocondensation leading to 2,4,5-trisubstituted imidazoles are achieved through the involvement of 1,2-diketone/ α -hydroxyketone, an aldehyde and ammonium acetate under microwave-assisted conditions³¹⁻³⁵, refluxing in acetic acid³⁶⁻³⁸, silica-sulphuric acid³⁹, NiCl₂.6H₂O/Al₂O₃⁴⁰, ZrCl₄⁴¹, ionic liquids⁴², ceric ammonium nitrate⁴³, oxalic acid⁴⁴, and InCl₃.3H₂O⁴⁵.

These methods, however, are applicable to certain synthetic conditions, use expensive reagents, demand longer reaction times, tedious work-up procedure, offer low selectivity and high catalyst loading during reaction run and eventually produce large amounts of toxic waste along with the desired product.

Reagents on inorganic solid supports are helping to develop many organic reactions and realizing desired products and these solid-supported reagents have several advantages over various conventional reagents. Reagents like iron(III) nitrate supported on K-10 montmorillonite, copper(II) nitrate supported on K-10 and, very recently, copper(II) nitrate supported on zeolite have successfully investigated for the formation of new carbon-carbon bonds in cycloaddition reactions⁴⁶. Furthermore, NH₄OAc supported on Al₂O₃⁴⁷, zeolite HY⁴⁸ and silica gel⁴⁹ have been already reported to accomplish highly substituted imidazoles.

In this article, we like to present a novel, mild and highly efficient method for the synthesis of tri- and tetrasubstituted imidazoles using supported reagents (Schemes 1 and 2) under microwave irradiation under solvent-free condition.

Scheme 1

Ar = Aryl, heteroaryl

Scheme 2

To the best of our knowledge, highly substituted imidazole molecules have never been reported taking ammonium formate as the ammonia donor, though there are very few reports in the literature where ammonium formate acted as the ammonia donor^{53,54}. This information promoted us to develop an efficient method to generate highly substituted imidazole based focused library. Ammonium formate is an attractive ammonia donor because of its low cost, easy availability and non-hazardous non-toxic nature. It is known that microwave irradiation has been utilized as one of the most convenient and efficient ways to promote organic reactions^{55,56}. In particular, the use of microwave energy to directly heat chemical reactions has become an increasingly popular technique in the scientific community and received, substantial interest because a variety of organic synthetic transformations can be carried out very efficiently and rapidly under environmentally benign conditions⁵¹⁻⁵⁹.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The typical procedure for 2,4,5-trisubstituted imidazoles involves impregnating the mixture of silica gel, ammonium formate with a dichloromethane solution of benzil, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde followed by solvent removal under reduced pressure. The mixture was then subjected to microwave irradiation under solvent free condition and was used as a model reaction to optimize the reaction conditions. Microwave irradiation under solvent-free system was found to be most rewarding in terms of yield of 1a (R¹ = NO₂) and reaction time (Table 1).

Table 1. Synthesis of 2,4,5-triaryl imidazole^a using different experimental conditions

Entry	Catalyst	Solvent	Reagent	Temp. (°C)	Time (min)	Reaction condition	Yield ^b (%)
1	–	EtOH	HCOONH ₄	80	1640	Reflux	40
2	Urotropine (20 mol%)	EtOH	HCOONH ₄	80	600	Reflux	60
3	KH ₂ PO ₄ (10 mol%)	EtOH	HCOONH ₄	80	600	Reflux	65
4	–	–	NH ₂ CONH ₂	95	5	MW	60
5	Silica gel (2.5 g)	–	NH ₂ CONH ₂	95	5	MW	65
6	–	–	HCOONH ₄	95	5	MW	75
7	Urotropine (20 mol%)	–	HCOONH ₄	95	5	MW	78
8	KH ₂ PO ₄ (10 mol%)	–	HCOONH ₄	95	5	MW	77
9	Neutral alumina (1.5 g)	–	HCOONH ₄	95	5	MW	90
10	Silica gel (2.5 g)	–	HCOONH ₄	95	5	MW	95

^aReagents used : 4-Nitrobenzaldehyde (1 mmol), benzil (1 mmol), ammonium formate (2.5 mmol), silica gel (2.5 g).

^bYields refer to isolated products.

From these experiments, it is also demonstrated that the silica gel-supported ammonium formate was the most effective combination for carrying out three-component cyclocondensation reaction. In order to evaluate the generality of the protocol, synthesis of 2,4,5-trisubstituted imidazoles **1a-m** were studied (Table 2).

Table 2. Ammonium formate-silica gel mediated synthesis of 2,4,5-trisubstituted imidazoles

Entry	Product	R ¹	Reaction time (min)		Yield (%) ^a	
			Benzil	Benzoin	Benzil	Benzoin
1	1a	4-NO ₂	5	7	95	93
2	1b	4-OMe	5	7	91	90
3	1c	4-F	5	7	92	90
4	1d	4-Br	5	7	92	90
5	1e	4-Cl	5	7	92	90
6	1f	4-OH	7	10	85	80
7	1g	H	5	7	93	92
8	1h	2-OH	7	10	82	80
9	1i	Furfural	5	7	90	87
10	1j	4-NMe ₂	6	8	95	92
11	1k	2-OH, 5-N=N-Ph	6	8	90	86
12	1l	4-CN	5	7	93	90
13	1m^b	4-Formyl	5	7	88	84

^aYields refer to pure isolated solid products, characterized by m.p., spectral (IR, ¹H, ¹³C and HR mass) data.

^bProduct is a bis-imidazole.

Cyclocondensation of benzil/benzoin with various aromatic aldehydes bearing electron-withdrawing groups (such as nitro, halide, nitrile and azo) or electron-releasing groups (such as hydroxyl, methoxy, dimethylamino groups) were carried out in the presence of ammonium formate supported on silica gel. The yields obtained were good to excellent without formation of any side products (Table 2). All the products obtained were fully characterized by spectroscopic methods such as IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectroscopy and also by comparison with the reported spectral data. The simplicity, together with the use of inexpensive, nontoxic reagent and tolerance to sensitive functionalities (like azo, nitrile, methoxy *etc.*) under solvent-free solid-state microwave reaction condition is the noteworthy feature of this procedure. In order to explore the applicability of this method, the same reaction conditions were applied for the synthesis of 1,2,4,5-tetrasubstituted imidazoles **2a-j** via a similar one-pot, four-component condensation of 1,2-diketone (1 mmol), aldehyde (1 mmol), amine (1 mmol) and ammonium formate (1.25 mmol) supported on silica gel (2.5 g), as depicted in Scheme 2. Generally the synthetic procedure employed was similar to that of trisubstituted imidazoles. Addition of ammonium formate impregnated on silica gel to a CH₂Cl₂ solution of benzil/benzoin, an aldehyde and an amine followed by evaporation of the solvent and finally upon microwave irradiation led to efficient formation of the desired products. The yields obtained were in the range of 70–95% (Table 3). There were no remarkable

Table 3. Ammonium formate-silica gel mediated synthesis of 1,2,4,5-tetrasubstituted imidazoles

Entry	Product	R ²	Ar	Reaction time (min)		Yield (%) ^a	
				Benzil as substrate	Benzoin as substrate	Benzil as substrate	Benzoin as substrate
1	2a	H		9	10	92	90
2	2b	H		10	12	88	82
3	2c	4-NO ₂		7	9	95	92
4	2d	4-NO ₂		8	10	90	87
5	2e	H		10	12	88	85
6	2f	4-OMe		10	12	84	80

7	2g	2-OH, 5- N=N-Ph N		6	9	89	85
8	2h	4-CN		8	10	85	80
9	2i	Furfural		5	7	90	86
10	2j	H		8	10	75	70

^aYields refer to pure isolated solid products, characterized by spectral (IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and HRMS) data.

difference in yields and reaction time between aryl aldehydes with electron-donating groups and those with electron-withdrawing groups. Moreover, aromatic and heteroaromatic amines both responded well to this reaction. Benzoin gave comparable yields as that of benzil but longer reaction times were required. The structures of compounds **2a-j** were determined from their IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectral data. The four-component condensation was also performed in the absence of silica gel under microwave irradiation; the yield of **2a** was low (~50%) demanding the presence of silica gel.

Absorption spectra :

To explore novel spectroscopic applications of the synthesized twenty-three highly substituted imidazole molecules we have carefully examined the structural features of the molecules. Three molecules [(2-(4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-phenol (**1h**), 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazophenol (**1k**) and 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1-thiazol-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazophenol (**2g**)] appeared to be interesting for spectral investigation because of possibility of intramolecular hydrogen bond between OH group and nitrogen center at the imidazole site leading to a six member hydrogen bonding network. The aromatic moieties are in conjugation among themselves forming a resonance-stabilized structure. Generally these types of molecular frameworks are capable for anions sensor by breaking of intramolecular hydrogen bonding and formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonding with the external anion unit⁶⁰⁻⁶². Comparative strength of intra- and intermolecular H-bond is the vital factor for anion sensing ability. Absorption spectra of the bare molecules **1k** and **2g** and in the presence of several anions

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of **1k** (CH₃CN) and **1k** (CH₃CN) with different anions (water) at room temperature. Molecule **1k** (CH₃CN) and anion concentration (water) are in the order of $5 \times 10^{-6} M$ and $20 \times 10^{-6} M$, respectively.

have been investigated at room temperature in polar solvent (CH₃CN) and are shown in Fig. 1. The bare molecule **1k** or **2g** showed its most intense absorption peak at 318 nm and a red-sided shoulder at 383 nm. The strong absorption band at 318 nm corresponds to the $\pi\pi^*$ transition of the imidazole chromophore unit as 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-phenol molecule has absorption band at the same position. Comparatively weak shoulder band at the red side may be due to the $n\pi^*$ transition. In presence of negative ions such as F⁻ and AcO⁻, the strongest peak at 318 nm divided into two peaks, one at 280 nm and another one at 339 nm. In addition to these two peaks a new red-sided strong peak appeared at 477 nm. In case of H₂PO₄⁻ ion similar new peak appeared at 477 nm. Notably **1h** with absorption peak at 318 nm showed very similar behavior where a new red shifted band at

~ 342 nm appeared in presence of anions. Therefore, we assigned this new peak as the absorption peak for the intermolecular hydrogen bonded complex. The presence of N=N-Ph in 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazophenol (**1k**) and 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1-thiazol-2-yl)-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazophenol (**2g**) is responsible for the observed large red shifted band at 477 nm in presence of anions. Due to less intermolecular hydrogen bonding ability of Cl⁻ and Br⁻ ions, these two anions were not capable for forming intermolecular hydrogen bond by breaking of strong intramolecular hydrogen bond. Thus the absorption spectra in presence of Cl⁻ and Br⁻ ions appeared to be same as that of the bare molecules **1k** and **2g**. As seen in Fig. 2, the colour of the solution distinctly changed from colorless to a faint brown colour indicating its anion sensing ability in the naked eye. Light absorbed at 477 nm for the intermolecular hydrogen bonded species showed its complementary colour in the naked eye. Therefore, these synthetic molecular systems can be used as naked eye and colorimetric sensor for anions when these anions are present in very minute quantity.

Fig. 2. Picture of solution containing **1k** (CH₃CN) (1) and **1k** with anions : acetate (2), F⁻ (3), dihydrogen phosphate (4), Cl⁻ (5), Br⁻ (6). **1k** : anion concentration used (1 . 2 equiv.).

Calculation of binding constant :

Fig. 3(a) shows the change in absorption intensity of 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazophenol (**1k**) with increasing F⁻ anion concentration. The binding constant of the ligand (**1k**) with F⁻ can be determined using Benesi-Hildebrand equation as follows;

$$K = \frac{[\mathbf{1k} : \text{F}^-]}{[\mathbf{1k}][\text{F}^-]}$$

Fig. 3. (a) Absorption titration curves for compound **1k** with different concentration of F⁻ ion concentration, (b) Benesi-Hildebrand plot.

where K is the binding constant in M⁻¹.

For these types of complexation process Benesi-Hildebrand relation is expressed as,

$$A = \frac{A_0 + A_1 K [\text{F}^-]}{1 + K [\text{F}^-]}$$

Rearranging the equation,

$$\frac{1}{(A - A_0)} = \frac{1}{(A_1 - A_0)} + \frac{1}{(A_1 - A_0) K [\text{F}^-]}$$

where A_0 , A and A_1 are the absorbance in absence of, at intermediate and infinite concentration of anion. The plot of $1/(A - A_0)$ vs $1/[\text{F}^-]$ shown in Fig. 1(b) gives a straight line for F⁻ indicating 1 : 1 complexation between **1k** and anion with very high binding constant ($K = 1.39 \times 10^4$ M⁻¹) with free energy change ($\Delta G^0 = -23.64$ kJ/mol⁻¹).

Conclusion :

To summarize, we have achieved a convenient and efficient procedure for the synthesis of tri- and tetra-substituted imidazoles through the one-pot cyclocondensation reaction using ammonium formate (as the ammonia source) supported on silica gel. The simple procedure combined with easy work-up involving highly economic and non-hazardous reagent combination will surely attract the chemist towards the synthesis of biologically and medicinally important tri- and tetra-substituted imidazoles. Finally, imidazoles, 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1*H*-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazophenol or 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1-thiazol-2-yl)-1*H*-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazophenol will be suitable as naked eye and colorimetric sensor where traces amount of anions like F⁻, Cl⁻, OAc⁻ and H₂PO₄⁻ are present.

Experimental*General information :*

Silica gel HF254 was purchased from Spectrochem, Bombay, India; ammonium formate from SD Laboratory, Bombay, India. The other organic reagents (aldehydes, amines, benzil and benzoin) were purchased from Aldrich and were used without further purification. The microwave instrument used was a CEM-DISCOVER Benchmate. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded using a BRUKER spectrometer operating at 300 MHz. All NMR measurements were carried out at 300 °C and chemical shifts are reported as ppm on the delta scale downfield from tetramethylsilane (TMS : δ = 0.00). Coupling constants (*J*) are reported in Hertz. Infrared spectra were recorded from KBr discs using a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. High Resolution Mass Spectra was obtained using a QTOFMICRO YA263 mass spectrometer. Melting points were determined using an Aluminium Block melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

Preparation of 2,4,5-triaryl imidazoles (1a-m) :

General procedure : To 2.5 g of silica gel in a 50 mL Rb flask was added 158 mg (2.5 mmol) ammonium formate (for trisubstituted imidazole) followed by diethyl ether (25 mL). The resulting solution was then stirred for 15 min at room temperature, solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to get ammonium formate-supported on silica gel and this can be directly used or can

be stored in a vacuum desiccator for at least seven days without loss in activity.

Benzil or benzoin (1 mmol), aldehyde (1 mmol), ammonium formate-supported on silica gel (158 mg impregnated on 2.5 g) in dichloromethane (10 mL) were taken in a 50 mL Rb flask and stirred at room temperature for 15 min. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the dry mass was then subjected to microwave irradiation (250 W, 95 °C) for specified time (Table 2). The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the crude product from the reaction mixture was treated with ethanol (20 mL) and the silica gel was separated by filtration. The filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure to remove ethanol, and the resulting product was washed with water (10 mL). The solid product was then crystallized from hot ethanol. After extraction of the product, silica gel was washed with acetone (3 × 10 mL) and dried under vacuum and can be used further by at least three times.

Synthesis of :

2-(4-Nitrophenyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazole (1a) : Triaryl imidazole **1a** was prepared according to our developed procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and was isolated as an orange solid. m.p. 200 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 3391 (N-H), 1597 (C=N), 1513 (NO₂), 1337 (NO₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 7.26–7.62 (10H, m), 8.05 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 8.26 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 124.3, 125.5, 127.8, 128.0, 128.7, 143.4.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazole (1b) : Triaryl imidazole **1b** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-methoxybenzaldehyde and was isolated as a white crystalline solid. m.p. 228 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 3416 (N-H), 1589 (C=N), 3184 (O-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 3.72 (3H, s), 6.81 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.17–7.23 (6H, m), 7.34–7.43 (4H, m), 7.7305 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 55.3, 114.3, 122.5, 126.9, 127.3, 127.8, 128.5, 132.7, 146.1, 160.2.

2-(4-Fluorophenyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazole (1c) : Triaryl imidazole **1c** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-fluorobenzaldehyde and was isolated as a white solid. m.p. 188 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 3451 (N-H), 1597 (C=N), 1665

(C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.23–7.56 (14H, m), 4.59 (1H, br.s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 118.2, 127.4, 127.5, 127.8, 121.9, 128.6, 131.7, 132.5.

2-(4-Bromophenyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazole (1d) : Triaryl imidazole **1d** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-bromobenzaldehyde and was isolated as a white crystalline solid. m.p. 260 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3421.7 (N–H), 1599.1 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.26–7.91 (13H, m), 8.19 (2H, d, J 13 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 126.7, 127.6, 127.8, 128.6, 132, 162.3.

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazole (1e) : Triaryl imidazole **1e** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-chlorobenzaldehyde and was isolated as a white crystalline solid. m.p. 258 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3424.1 (N–H), 1600.8 (C=N), 1485.5 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.81 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.260–7.539 (13H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 126.4, 127.5, 127.8, 128.6, 129.1, 143.1.

4-(4,5-Diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-phenol (1f) : Triaryl imidazole **1f** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and was isolated as a white crystalline solid. m.p. 266 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3051.1 (N–H), 1567 (C=N), 2916 (O–H); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.26–7.98 (16H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 118, 129, 129.9, 133, 134.8, 162.3.

2,4,5-Triphenyl-1H-imidazole (1g) : Triaryl imidazole **1g** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with benzaldehyde and was isolated as a white crystalline solid. m.p. 278 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3422 (N–H), 1593 (C=N), 1667 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.26–7.56 (14H, m), 7.91 (2H, d, J 7 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 125.3, 127.4, 127.8, 127.9, 128.6, 128.9, 129, 129.9, 134.9.

2-(4,5-Diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-phenol (1h) : Triaryl imidazole **1h** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde and was isolated as a white crystalline solid. m.p. 192 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3410 (N–H), 3192 (O–H), 1589 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 6.86–7.49 (14H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 112.5, 117.8, 119, 123.2, 127.8, 128.7, 130.5, 145.7, 157.4,

162.3.

2-Furan-2-yl-4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazole (1i) : Triaryl imidazole **1i** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with furfural and was isolated as a brown crystalline solid. m.p. 235 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3410 (N–H), 1599 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 6.513 (1H, dd, J 2 Hz), 7 (1H, d, J 4 Hz), 7.250–7.528 (11H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 107.7, 112.1, 127.5, 127.8, 128.6, 138.9, 142.3.

[4-(4,5-Diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-phenyl]-dimethylamine (1j) : Triaryl imidazole **1j** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-*N,N'*-dimethylamino benzaldehyde and was isolated as a white crystalline solid. m.p. 256 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3430 (N–H), 1611.2 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 2.969 (6H, s), 6.69 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz), 7.250–7.51 (10H, m), 7.80 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 40.2, 112.1, 117.1, 126.7, 127.2, 127.9, 128.4, 131.7, 132.5, 146.8, 150.8.

2-(4,5-Diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazo-phenol (1k) : Triaryl imidazole 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazo-phenol was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 2-hydroxy-5-azophenyl benzaldehyde and was isolated as an orange solid. m.p. 162 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3754 (N–H), 3138 (O–H), 1602 (C=N), 1405 (N=N); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, 300 MHz) : δ 6.89–7.86 (19H, m), 8.73 (1H, bs, OH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, 75 MHz) : δ 117.7, 117.8, 121.3, 122.1, 123.8, 128.7, 129.4, 145.1, 159.8; HRMS Calcd. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}$ ($[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$) 417.1716; Found : 417.3899.

4-(4,5-Diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-benzonitrile (1l) : Triaryl imidazole **1l** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-cyanobenzaldehyde and was isolated as a white crystalline solid. m.p. 264 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3406 (N–H), 2224.3 (C≡N), 1601.4 (C=N), 1686.9 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.321–7.387 (6H, m), 7.553 (4H, d, J 5.7 Hz), 7.72 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 8.02 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 125.4, 127.8, 128.7, 132.7, 143.7, 162.3.

Bis imidazole (1m) : Bis-triaryl imidazole **1m** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-formylbenzaldehyde and was isolated as a

yellow crystalline solid. m.p. > 300 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3410.6 (N-H), 1594.4 (C=N); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.198–7.550 (20H, m), 8.72 (4H, s); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 75 MHz) : δ 117.7, 125.4, 126.6, 127.1, 127.8, 128.2, 128.4, 128.7, 129.9, 131.0, 135.1, 137.4, 142.2, 145.2.

Preparation of 1,2,4,5-tetraaryl imidazoles (2a-j) :

General procedure : For tetrasubstituted imidazole; 80 mg (1.25 mmol) ammonium formate was used along with 2.5 g silica gel and diethyl ether (25 mL), stirred for 15 min, followed by solvent removal under reduced pressure.

Benzil or benzoin (1 mmol), aldehyde (1 mmol), amine (1 mmol), ammonium formate-supported on silica gel (80 mg impregnated on 2.5 g) in dichloromethane (10 mL) were taken in a 50 mL Rb flask and stirred at room temperature for 15 min. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the dry mass was then subjected to microwave irradiation (250 W, 95 °C) for specified time (Table 3). The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the crude product from the reaction mixture was treated with hot ethanol (25 mL) and the silica gel was separated by filtration. The filtrate was removed under reduced pressure to remove ethanol, and the resulting product was washed with water (10 mL). The solid product was then crystallized from hot ethanol.

1,2,4,5-Tetraaryl-1H-imidazole (2a) : Tetraaryl imidazole **2a** was prepared according to our developed procedure on a similar scale starting with benzaldehyde and aniline and was isolated as a white crystalline solid. m.p. 218 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 1596 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.03–7.98 (20H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 126.6, 127.4, 128.1, 128.3, 128.4, 129, 130.7, 131.1, 134.4, 137.1, 138.2, 143.3, 146.9.

1-(4-Chloro-phenyl)-2,4,5-triphenyl-1H-imidazole (2b) : Tetraaryl imidazole **2b** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with benzaldehyde and 4-chloroaniline and was isolated as a white solid. m.p. 224 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3042.8 (C-N), 1596.4 (C=N), 1674.0 (C=C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 6.869–7.791 (19H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75

MHz) : δ 118.1, 126.6, 127.3, 128.1, 128.2, 128.4, 128.5, 128.9, 129.2, 129.5, 130.2, 130.3, 130.6, 131.0, 134.11, 134.1, 135.6, 138.4, 146.9; HRMS Calcd. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{19}\text{ClN}_2$ ($[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$) 407.1315; Found : 407.2428.

2-(4-Nitro-phenyl)-1,4,5-triphenyl-1H-imidazole (2c) : Tetraaryl imidazole **2c** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and aniline and was isolated as a yellow crystalline solid. m.p. 190 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 1596.4 (C=N), 1514.9 (NO_2), 1340.3 (NO_2); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 6.977–7.307 (13H, m), 7.482–7.540 (4H, m), 7.986–8.024 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 123.4, 127.0, 127.3, 128.2, 128.3, 128.4, 129.0, 129.5, 129.9, 131.0, 132.4, 133.8, 136.5, 136.6, 139.3, 144.3, 147.0.

1-(2-Methoxyphenyl, 2-(4-nitrophenyl)-4,5-triphenyl-1H-imidazole (2d) : Tetraaryl imidazole **2d** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and 2-methoxyaniline and was isolated as an orange yellow crystalline solid. m.p. 192 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 1596.5 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 3.536 (3H, s), 6.853–7.362 (12H, m), 7.595–7.682 (4H, m), 8.066–8.111 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 55.3, 112.1, 120.9, 123.3, 125.5, 126.8, 127.1, 128.1, 128.3, 129.7, 130.3, 130.5, 132.6, 134.0, 136.9, 138.9, 144.6, 147.0, 154.9; MASS Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$ ($[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$) 448.17; Found : 448.30.

2,4,5-Triphenyl-1-thiophen-2-ylmethyl-1H-imidazole (2e) : Tetraaryl imidazole **2e** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with benzaldehyde and thiophene 2-methyl amine and was isolated as an Off white solid. m.p. 228 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 1594 (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 5.227 (2H, s), 6.39 (1H, d, J 3.4 Hz), 6.76 (1H, d, J 3.4 Hz), 7.09–7.82 (16H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 43.8, 125.1, 126.4, 126.6, 128, 128.8, 128.9, 129.1, 129.3, 129.6, 130.9, 131.2, 134.3, 138, 139.8, 142.4, 147.8; HRMS Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{S}$ ($[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$) 393.1425; Found : 393.1920.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1,4,5-triphenyl-1H-imidazole (2f) : Tetraaryl imidazole **2f** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-methoxybenzaldehyde and aniline and was isolated as a yellow crystal-

line solid. m.p. 178 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 1600.1 (C=N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 3.664 (3H, s), 6.581–7.283 (17H, m), 7.5 (2H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 55.1, 113.4, 123.0, 126.4, 127.3, 127.7, 128.0, 128.0, 128.2, 128.4, 128.9, 130.2, 130.4, 130.7, 131.0, 134.4, 137.1, 137.9, 146.8, 159.5.

2-(4,5-Diphenyl-1-thiazol-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazophenol (2g) : Tetraaryl imidazole 2-(4,5-diphenyl-1-thiazol-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-4-phenylazo-phenol was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 2-hydroxy 5-azophenyl benzaldehyde and 2-amino thiazole and was isolated as an orange solid. m.p. 154 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 3424.4 (N-H), 3052.5 (O-H), 1597.3 (C=N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 7.03–7.919 (20H, m), 8.06 (1H, bs, O-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 106.6, 112.7, 117.2, 118.3, 122.5, 126.6, 127.7, 128.7, 129.0, 130.4, 142.9, 145.1, 145.2, 145.3, 152.6, 160.5; LCMS Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₁N₅OS ([M+H]⁺) 500.15; Found : 500.38. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₁N₅OS ([M+Na]⁺) 522.14, Found : 522.37.

4-(1,4,5-Triphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-benzotrile (2h) : Tetraaryl imidazole **2h** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with 4-cyano benzaldehyde and aniline and was isolated as a yellow crystalline solid. m.p. 186 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 1597.8 (C=N), 2221.5 (C=N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 6.974–7.470 (19H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 111.4, 118.1, 118.5, 126.9, 127.2, 128.2, 128.4, 128.8, 129.4, 129.9, 130.9, 131.8, 132.1, 133.9, 134.6, 136.6, 139.0, 144.5; HRMS Calcd. for C₂₈H₁₉N₃ ([M+H]⁺) 398.1657; Found : 398.1657.

2-Furan-2-yl-1,4,5-triphenyl-1H-imidazole (2i) : Tetraaryl imidazole **2i** was prepared following the same procedure on a similar scale starting with furfural and aniline and was isolated as an Off white crystalline solid. m.p. 212 °C, IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 1595.1 (C=N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 5.663 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz), 6.169 (1H, dd, *J* 3 Hz), 6.974–7.490 (16H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 109.3, 110.9, 126.6, 127.4, 128.0, 128.3, 128.5, 128.9, 129.1, 130.0, 130.7, 130.9, 134.0, 136.6, 138.5, 139.4, 142.7, 144.8; LCMS Calcd for C₂₅H₁₈N₂O ([M+H]⁺) 363.15; Found : 363.21.

2-(2,4,5-Triphenyl-imidazole-1-yl)-pyridine (2j) : Tetraaryl imidazole **2j** was prepared following the same

procedure on a similar scale starting with benzaldehyde and 2-amino pyridine and was isolated as a white solid m.p. 258 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 3436 (N-H), 1592 (C=N), 1663 (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 7.13–7.98 (19H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 125.3, 127.5, 127.8, 128.5, 128.8, HRMS Calcd for C₂₆H₁₉N₃ ([M+H]⁺) 374.1658; Found : 374.3207

Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge the financial support from UGC and Calcutta University PB thanks CSIR for his fellowship (Grant No. 09/028(0768)/2010-EMR1)

References

- 1 J Heers, L J Backx, J H Mostmans and J Van Cutsem *J Med Chem*, 1979, 22, 1003
- 2 W Hunkeler, H Mohler, L Pieri, P Polc, E P Bonetti R Cumin, R Schaffner and W Haefely, *Nature*, 1979, 290 514
- 3 R W Brimblecombe, W A M Duncan, G J Durant, J C Emmett, C R Ganellin and M E Parons, *J Int Med Res*, 1975, 3, 86
- 4 Y Tanigawara, N Aoyama, T Kita, K Shirakawa, F Komada, M Kusuga and K Okumura, *Clin Pharmacol Ther*, 1999, 66, 528
- 5 A Wauquier, W A E Van Den Broeck, J L Verheyen and P A Janssen, *J Eur J Pharmacol*, 1978, 47, 367
- 6 M Antolini, A Bozzoli, C Ghiron, G Kennedy, T Rossi and A Ursini, *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*, 1999, 9, 1023
- 7 L Wang, K W Woods, Q Li, K J Barr, R W McCroskey, S M Hannick, L Gherke, R B Credo, Y H Hui, K Marsh, R Warner, J Y Lee, N Zielinsky-Mozng, D Frost, S H Rosenberg and H L Sham, *J Med Chem*, 2002, 45, 1697
- 8 J C Lee, J T Laydon, P C McDonnell, T F Gallagher, S Kumar, D Green, D McNulty, M J Blumenthal, J R Keys, S W L Vatter, J E Strickler, M M McLaughlin, I R Siemens, S M Fisher, G P Livi, J R White, J L Adams and P R Young, *Nature*, 1994, 372, 739
- 9 A K Takle, M J B Brown, S Davies, O K Dean, G Francis, A Gaiba, A W Hird, F D King, P J Lovell A Naylor, A D Reith, J G Steadman and D M Wilson, *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*, 2006, 16, 378
- 10 S E de Laszlo, C Hacker, B Li, D Kim, M MacCoss, N Mantalo, J V Pivnichny, L Colwell G E Koch, M A Cascieri and W K Hagmann, *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*, 1999, 9, 641
- 11 R Schmierer, H Mildenberger and H Buerstell, German Patent 361464, 1987 (*Chem Abstr*, 1988, 108 37838)

12. J. Heeres, L. J. J. Backx, J. H. Mostmans and J. Van Custem, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1979, **22**, 1003.
13. T. Maier, R. Schmierer, K. Bauer, H. Bieringer, H. Buerstell and B. Sachse, US Patent 4820335, 1989 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1989, 111, 19494w).
14. R. R. Nagawade and D. B. Shinde, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 2007, **54**, 642.
15. B. Radziszewski, *Chem. Ber.*, 1882, **15**, 1493.
16. F. R. Japp and H. H. Robinson, *Chem. Ber.*, 1882, **15**, 1268.
17. S. Balalaie and A. Arabanian, *Green Chem.*, 2002, **2**, 274.
18. M. Kidwai, P. Mothsra, V. Bansal, R. K. Somvanshi, A. S. Ethayathulla, S. Dey and P. Singh, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2007, **265**, 177.
19. S. Kantevari, S. V. N. Vuppalapati, D. O. Biradar and L. Nagarapu, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2007, **266**, 109.
20. M. M. Heravi, F. Derikvand and F. F. Bamoharram, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2007, **263**, 112.
21. L. Nagarapu, S. Apuri and S. Kantevari, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2007, **266**, 104.
22. A. R. Karimi, Z. Alimohammadi, J. Azizian, A. A. Mohammadi and M. R. Mohammadzadeh, *Catal. Commun.*, 2006, **7**, 728.
23. S. Samai, G. C. Nandi, P. Singh and S. Singh, *Tetrahedron*, 2009, **65**, 10155.
24. M. M. Heravi, F. Derikvand and M. Haghighi, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 2008, **139**, 31.
25. B. Sadeghi, B. B. F. Mirjalili and M. M. Hashemi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2008, **49**, 2575.
26. C. Mukhopadhyay, P. K. Tapaswi and M. G. B. Drew, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2010, **51**, 3944.
27. A. R. Karimi, Z. Alimohammadi and M. M. Amini, *Mol. Divers.*, 2009, doi: 10.1007/s11030-009-9197-x.
28. S. Balalaie, M. M. Hashem and M. Akhbari, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 1709.
29. I. Lantos, W. Y. Zhang, X. Shui and D. S. Eggleston, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 7092.
30. D. Davidson, M. Weiss and M. Jelling, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1937, **2**, 319.
31. A. Y. Usyatinsky and Y. L. Khmel'nitsky, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2000, **41**, 5031.
32. S. E. Wolkenberg, D. D. Wisnoski, W. H. Leister, Y. Wang, Z. Zhao and C. W. Lindslui, *Org. Lett.*, 2004, **6**, 1453.
33. R. B. Sparks and A. P. Combs, *Org. Lett.*, 2004, **6**, 2473.
34. H. A. Oskooie, Z. Alimohammadi and M. M. Heravi, *Heteroat. Chem.*, 2006, **17**, 699.
35. E. Chauveau, C. Marestin, F. Schiets and R. Mercier, *Green Chem.*, 2010, **12**, 1018.
36. J. Wang, R. Mason, D. V. Derveer, K. Feng and X. R. Bu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 5415.
37. S. Sarshar, D. Siev and M. M. Mjalli, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, **37**, 835.
38. T. F. Gallagher, G. L. Seibel, S. Kassis, J. T. Laydon, M. J. Blumenthal, J. C. Lee, D. Lee, J. C. Boehm, S. M. Fier-Thompson, J. W. Abt, M. E. Soreson, J. M. Smietana, R. F. Hall, R. S. Garigipati, P. E. Bender, K. F. Erhard, A. J. Krog, G. A. Hofmann, P. L. Sheldrake, P. C. McDonnell, S. Kumar, P. R. Young and J. L. Adams, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 1997, **5**, 49.
39. A. Shaaban and A. Rahmati, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2006, **249**, 246.
40. M. M. Heravi, K. Bakhtiari, H. A. Oskooie and S. Taheri, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2007, **263**, 279.
41. G. V. M. Sharma, Y. Jyothi and P. S. Lakshmi, *Synth. Commun.*, 2006, **36**, 2991.
42. S. A. Siddiqui, U. C. Narkhede, S. S. Palimkar, P. Daniel, R. J. Lahoti and K. V. Srinivasan, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 3539.
43. J. N. Sangshetti, N. D. Kokare, S. A. Kotharkara and D. B. Shinde, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2008, **5**, 463.
44. N. D. Kokare, J. N. Sangshetti and D. B. Shinde, *Synthesis*, 2007, **18**, 2829.
45. S. Das Sharma, P. Hazarika and D. Konwar, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2008, **49**, 2216.
46. P. Laszlo and J. Lucchetti, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, **25**, 1567.
47. P. Laszlo and J. Lucchetti, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, **25**, 2147.
48. P. Laszlo and J. Lucchetti, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, **25**, 4387.
49. K. Sivakumar, A. Kathirvel and A. Lalitha, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2010, **51**, 3018.
50. A. Usyatinsky and Y. L. Khmel'nitsky, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2000, **41**, 5031.
51. S. Balalaie, A. Arabanian and M. Hashtroudi, MOCMB7; *Monatshefte fuer Chemie*, 2000, **9**, 945.
52. Y. Xu, Li. F. Wan, H. Salehi, W. Deng, Guo and X. Qing, *Heterocycles*, 2004, **63**, 1613.
53. K. B. Fox and A. Evans (Jr.), Eur. Pat. Appl., 1994.
54. M. E. Ducote and C. L. Green (Jr.), US patent 4531989, 1985.
55. C. O. Kappe, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2004, **43**, 6250.

Bhattacharyya *et al.* : Silica gel-mediated microwave-assisted efficient synthesis of highly substituted *etc.*

56. D. R. Ding, X. Li, X. Wang, Y. L. Du and J. K. Shen, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 6997.
57. A. Loupy, A. Petti, J. Hamelin, F. Texier-Boullet, P. Jacquault and D. Mathe, *Synthesis*, 1998, 1213.
58. H. F. Motiwala, R. Kumar and A. K. Chakraborty, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 2007, **60**, 369.
59. M. Jeselnik, R. S. Varma, S. Polanc and M. Kocevar, *Chem. Commun.*, 2001, **21**, 1716.
60. X. J. Mu, M. Y. Lei and J. P. Zou, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 1125.
61. Y. Li, J. Li, H. Un, J. Shao and Z. S. Cai, *J. Lumin.*, 2010, **130**, 466
62. T. Ghosh, B. G. Maiya and M. W. Wong, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2004, **108**, 11249
63. E. J. Cho, J. W. Moon, S. W. Ko, J. Y. Lee, S. K. Kim, J. Yoon and K. C. Nam, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 12376.

